

Societal & Political Engagement
of Young People in Environmental Issues

D2.4: Report on Co-Production of Services

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Executive summary

The STEP project aims to open up information and participative decision-making processes of environmental issues within a region or municipality. The STEP project (STEP.Green platform) specifically targets Young European Citizens to increase their participation in decision-making procedures, policy process, collaborating with others, and reaching consensus to bring about positive and effective responses to environmental related issues. STEP also targets Public Authorities to enable open information, participatory processes and response to petitions in order to produce the greatest gains in effective local and regional governance, and utilise the participation of young citizens as a policy-making tool. STEP's main output is a cloud based and modular e-Participation SaaS platform, (available as a mobile application and through a web platform), to open, manage and integrate participatory decision making with youngsters regarding environmental issues in regular practices.

The Deliverable *D2.4 –STEP Report on Co-Production of Services* - is the final Deliverable of **Work Package 2 Requirements and Analysis**. The purpose of this deliverable is to present the activities conducted for the Co-Production of Services for the STEP Platform. The intended audience for this deliverable is primarily the project partners, however, the research work conducted for the definition of requirements will be of interest for a wider audience (e.g. policy makers, researchers, the public).

User requirements have been extended and refined by running various Co-Production / Co-Design workshops with the end-users of the platform (both Young European Citizens and Policy Makers / Public Officers). As the challenges of designing complex systems such as e-Participation platforms increase, traditional user-centered design processes alone are not enough to ensure a usable and desirable end-product. Having stakeholders engage in the early design process not only increases the engagement and ownership of the platform by those users but as the users are experts of their own lives and experiences, they bring these insights into the design process and are able to influence the development of the platform.

1 Co-Production of Services

This deliverable highlights the co-creation work carried out with young European citizens and other stakeholders (eg. Public Officers) to improve the STEP platform and ensure that it fully meets the requirements of all end-users. We will discuss here the evolution of the co-design / co-creation process and the practical use of the methodology undertaken with Pilot partners and other end-users to inform the development process. There are several terms used to describe the participatory approach to designing both systems and services; these include Co-Production, Co-Creation, Co-Design and Co-Delivery. Throughout this deliverable the term co-design is favored when describing the work we carried out with young people and Policy makers. When discussing the literature, the term used by the original researcher has been used.

1.1 History of Co-creation to inform Design

Designers have become increasingly aware of the need to understand their end users, and this is apparent in the shift towards a User-centred design approach. End-users can be a rich source of product and service innovation (Prahalad & Ramaswamy, 2000)(Vargo & Lusch, 2004). In the literature, the participation of end-users is often labelled 'co-creation' (Von Hippel, 1988) and the terms Co-creation / Co-Design are the more recent terms used for what the Scandinavian researchers called Participatory design (PD)-which has been around for approximately 40 years. In the mid-1970's, computer-based technologies were introduced into the workplace in Europe, and workers began to feel that they were losing control of their work environment. The early Scandinavian Co-operative Design movement actually involved very little actual design *per se*. but emphasized the importance of providing workers and union officials the knowledge and skills about the potential of computational systems so that their views would be better articulated when bargaining with management. The PD approach brings together the expertise of the systems designers/researchers and the situated expertise of the people whose work was to be impacted by the change. The approach, thus, built on the workers' own experiences and provided them with the resources to be able to act in their current situation (Bodker, 1996).

It has been argued (Carroll & Rosson, 2007) that user participation is primarily motivated by the moral proposition 'that the people whose activity and experiences will ultimately be affected most directly by a design outcome ought to have a substantive say in what that outcome is'. In the 1980s and 1990s, a 'citizen-centred revolution' took place and used tools such as client feedback (customer-satisfaction surveys) to give users a role in service improvement (Lenihan & Briggs, 2011). Co-design (another more recent term for co-creation / participatory design) is the next stage in the process of citizen centred 'movement' and co-design has been used in government, community and health sectors to extend traditional consultation methods and increase the reach and impact across an array of policy and programme areas (Lenihan & Briggs, 2011).

Co-creation aims to break down hierarchies between local government, business, academia, citizens and other stakeholders. Ideally, it should lead to greater innovation, better targeting of resources and an increased sense of ownership of projects and their outcomes¹¹. Co-creation is based on the belief

¹ <https://www.siliconcape.com/using-human-behaviour-to-make-better-cities/> accessed December 2016

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that the users' presence is essential in the creative process, as the users provide insight into what is valuable to them. At its core, this means that co-creation is literally any process that brings together users and designers to work toward a shared goal. In practice, this often takes the form of a collaborative workshop in which business stakeholders, researchers, designers, and end-users explore a problem and generate solutions together, taking into account their different approaches, needs, and points of view. Technology innovations, particularly the increase in social media use meant that it became much easier to engage end-users and co-creation has become a driving force in marketing techniques of some companies. The end goal of co-creation is the same as that of research and concept design: to identify a solution that provides users with better experiences, and organizations with improved and innovative services.²²

Co-design not only influences customer satisfaction and loyalty, but also helps firms to achieve competitive advantage (Grissmann & Stokburger-Sauer, 2012) and to create value through interaction (Galvagno & Dalli, 2014). Two recent literature reviews on Co-Design / Co-creation have been carried out (Galvagno & Dalli, 2014); and (Voorberg, Bekkers, & Tummers, 2014).

It is apparent though that the traditional user-centred design approach (mainly used to develop products) cannot address the complexity of the challenges we face today (Sanders & Stappers, 2008). There has been a shift away from simply designing new products towards designing for the future experiences of people, communities and cultures. The fields of 'service design' and 'interaction design' have become more widely adopted. Emerging design practices, such as 'design for sustainability' or 'design for transforming;' are based on personal or societal needs. Sanders & Stappers, (2008) argue that these emerging design disciplines require larger scopes of inquiry and a longer-term viewpoint to be taken.

The fuzzy front-end (Sanders & Stappers, 2008) describes the phase at the start of a Development process, this is the time when ideas may be numerous, varied and 'fuzzy' ie not well defined. This period is then followed by the design development process, where the resulting ideas for products are then refined and developed into concepts, prototypes, and then further refined into resulting products or services. The fuzzy front-end phase is important as the early phases of the development process offer the greatest opportunity for transformational innovation. The diagrams below attempt to describe this process.

Figure 1.1 Sanders and Stappers' (2008), model for co-designing.

²² <http://www.uxbooth.com/articles/co-creation-designing-with-the-user-for-the-user/> accessed Dec 2016

Figure 1.2 The original framework: Three approaches to making are located along a timeline of the design process. (Sanders & Stappers, 2014)

Figure 1.3 Three approaches to making are positioned relative to the mindsets and phases in the design process. (Sanders & Stappers, 2014)

Co-design activities take place predominantly during the concept design, and even when spread throughout the design cycle most design activities end when the product is taken into use (Botero & Hyysalo, 2013).

The diagram above (Fig 1.3) shows the different perspectives of the use of probes, toolkits and prototypes within the design process and highlights the difference between ‘designing for’ and ‘designing with’.

1.2 The STEP Approach

As part of the user centred approach to the design of the STEP platform, we have utilised all these different methodologies. The insights found from our Cultural Probe were reported in D4.1 and were useful in giving us a ‘glimpse’ of how young people could interact with the platform and with each

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other via the platform. So far we have been carrying out design activities within the generative phase of the design process. With the prototype STEP platform now available, we will continue our activities within the evaluative framework. For the STEP project, we began carrying out Co-Design workshops early in the project life-cycle, but have continued to run more workshops throughout the middle stages of the project. Results have been fed back to developers to enable end-users' needs to be considered. The co-design of the STEP platform for young people and policy-makers/public officers (i.e. the people comprising our platform's end users) is important as they have direct interest, insider's experiences and the knowledge and skills to inform the design process. We believe that they are likely to enjoy the process of co-design and feel that it will promote 'ownership' of the platform by incorporating some of their ideas.

Research and Development companies developing digital products and services (Bessant et al, 2015) increasingly use co-design involving young people. Many examples of the literature highlighting how young people have been involved with co-design activities have been in the field of health service policy and delivery (Sustar et al., 2013; Truman & Raine, 2002; Bowen, Sustar, Wolstenholme, & Dearden, 2013). There have also been efforts to include young people in community development, for example the Teen Design Days that explores concepts, test ideas and builds ICT solutions with young people (Fisher, Bishop, & Fawcett, 2013). These teen design days (TDD) draw upon methodologies from participatory design, community-based action research and social network analysis. Fisher et al, 2013 conclude from this work that youth are one of society's biggest assets and that a lot can be accomplished when a youth-focused, action-oriented framework that emphasizes fun instead of research is used. For the STEP research undertaken as part of Task 2.4, we have aimed to ensure the activities we engaged young people in were as much fun as possible. Having 'enjoyable' co-design activities for young people to take part in will ensure that their participation is both rewarding to them as well as productive for the project. Having for example, pre-existing 'tablet' templates (see figure 2.1) to sketch in tends to stimulate their creativity and get ideas flowing – rather than presenting them with a blank piece of paper. Having young people work in small groups also makes the experience more enjoyable and social than asking them to work on their own.

Co-Creation for Citizen Engagement:

Policy makers and politicians consider co-creation/co-production with citizens as an important process to create innovative public services that actually meet the needs of citizens; it seems to be considered as a cornerstone for social innovation in the public sector (Voorberg et al., 2014). Design for civic engagement should involve young people in the development of content, and in cases that are relevant and compatible with their cultural lifestyles. (Brandztaeg et al. 2012). STEP has included over 130 young people and over 30 policy makers / public officers in the co-design process. The inclusion of these people has not only generated interesting design ideas but has helped to increase youth engagement with environmental issues and with the STEP project.

Figure 1.4 The map of design research, showing different approaches laid along two axes: role of the user (horizontal), and approach of the research (vertical). Source: From Sanders and Stappers (2008).

1.2.1 Tools to Aid Creativity

In order for Users to become part of the design team as ‘experts of their experiences’ they must be given appropriate tools for expressing themselves (Sleeswijk Visser & Visser, 2006). Recently, in the last 10 years or so there has been a lot of interest in exploring co-designing tools and techniques.

IDEO’s downloadable toolkit (Ideo, 2011) and the useful methodology resources provided online at (<http://www.designkit.org>) provide useful design guides to encourage practitioners to think in a more ‘design-led’ way when undertaking user research, including co-design workshops. The toolkit offers techniques, methods, tips, and worksheets to aid the process that gives voice to communities and allows their desires to guide the creation and implementation of solutions. The toolkit and the web resources have both been consulted when planning the co-design workshops for STEP. The card-sort method used in gathering information about ‘issues of trust’ was taken from this resource (<http://www.designkit.org/methods/24>).

Figure 1.5 From IDEO's toolkit Showing the three lenses of Human Centred Design (Ideo, 2011).

Other sources of inspiration for the co-design activities were the book Undercover User Experience Design (by Bowles & Box, 2010) and the work carried out at Young Scot (<http://www.youngscot.net/what-we-do/co-design-service/>).

As we have involved Young people early in the decision making process through our highly participative approach, we believe we have informed insights, ideas, recommendations and solutions for both the STEP platform and for Youth engagement policy and practice. We are implementing those features that fall within the centre of the above diagram, ie those that are feasible, viable and desirable.

1.3 Planning the Co-Creation Workshops

The Pilot partners are a heterogenous group, each having their own unique aspects; for example, the demographics of the populations varies greatly between the Pilots. Each region will have their own local difficulties, such as youth unemployment, disengagement, as well as positive aspects, for example -some pilots have a lot of previous experience engaging with young people on environmental issues. For the Pilots with less experience with citizen participation then there will be a lot to consider

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and learn, co-operation between the pilot partners has enabled previous lessons learned to be shared.

As the STEP platform needs to fulfill the needs of all end-users across all the pilot areas, we carried out workshops across all the different Pilots to ensure that a wide range of end users participate in the Co-Design process. The workshops are grouped by the type of activity that was covered rather than the chronological order of the events. Some images from the workshops have been included in the results section, the rest have been included as an appendix at the end of this deliverable. Pilot partners offered support in finding and recruiting participants, the practicalities of finding a suitable physical location to run the workshops and in translation and language support where needed. The Pilot Partners with support also led some workshops from Abertay University, such as the Valdemoro Young European Citizen series of workshops, and the Calabria, Prague and Hatay workshops. Help and support was also provided during the sessions led by Abertay, for example, a translator was provided at the Crete workshop and help provided by local partners during the session.

Table 1.1 Co-Design sessions run for Task 2.4

Place	Country	Focus	Involved	Number / gender	Date
Abertay University	UK	Engagement / Fun/ Gamification	Young People (students 18-25)	33 27M 6F	October 2015
Valdemoro	Spain	Ensuring Elements for Services match	Policy Makers	21 12M 9F	January 2016
Mollet del Vallés	Spain	Personalisation elements for STEP	Young People (High School students 16-18)	12 5M 7F	February 2016
Heraklion	Crete, Greece	Issues of Trust	Mix Policy Makers/ Young People	20 12M 10F	April 2016
Prague	Czech Republic	General Design elements	Young People	7 3M 4F	May 2016
Valdemoro (High School)	Spain	General Design elements / Personalisation	Young People (High School Students 16-18)	25 20M 5F	May 2016
Calabria	Italy	Role Play exercise	Young People	15 6M 9F	June 2016
Hatay	Turkey	Personalisation elements for STEP	Young People	21 12M 9F	November 2016
Dundee local Youth Group	UK	Explore current Design elements	Young People (less opportunities)	8 4M 4F	December 2016

1.4 Enhancing the Engagement of Young People with an E-Participation Platform

1.4.1 Methods:

This workshop was conducted in Dundee (UK) with a class comprised of thirty students (mostly aged 18-20 with a few slightly older, and an additional two 16-17 year old school students (who were visiting the University on placement). The students were given a brief (5-minute) overview of the project 2 days before the session was held. On the day, they were given another quick overview and asked to work in groups of three for the 2-hour session. Students were reminded that the aim of the project was to increase engagement with Environmental Issues & Policy Discussion. For this session, they were not given any information about the design of the proposed platform (ie STEP).

1.4.1.1 Idea Generation for Increasing Engagement with the STEP Platform

Students were informed that there were no constraints to their ideas (technical / budget etc). Ideas were written on Post-it notes and attached to a large sheet of paper. At the end of the process (about 30-40 minutes), each group's best idea was presented by a spokesperson from the group to the rest of the class.

1.4.1.2 Design for a specific person (using Personas)

Student groups were assigned one of the 8 Personas created for STEP (reported in D2.2) and asked to either design an interface that this person would find appealing or write a list of features that would increase their engagement. Having a Persona helps to give a more concrete character set, which tends to generate more design ideas than just a generic person does. The Personas were based on the user research undertaken in the first period of Work Package 2 for STEP.

1.5 General Co-Design Workshops

These Co-Design workshops were run at the following locations:

- Mollet del Valles (Spain)
- Valdemoro (Spain)
- Prague (Czech Republic)
- Hatay

1.5.1 General Co-Design Methodology

Session co-ordinators were defined and informed before the start of the session to ensure they knew what procedure to follow on the day.

Prior to each of the sessions, participants were given information sheets and informed consent forms (including parental consent if required for under 18's); these were then signed and collected.

The number of participants taking part was dependent on how many people were available to co-ordinate the session. If one or two people are available, the numbers should comprise between 6 and

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20 participants (if more co-ordinators are available to run the session then more participants could be involved, but it was necessary to maintain manageable numbers). Ideally the participants should work in groups of 3-4 people.

Introduction:

Time 10 minutes

Participants were given an overview of the STEP project via Powerpoint presentation.

1.5.1.1 Designing the Welcome Page for the Platform

Thinking about a space to promote interaction & engagement with your City Council on environmental policies :

Explain to participants that there are no constraints for their ideas (technical / budget etc.)

- Sketch a welcome page for your Local Community STEP Website (aimed at Young People 16-29) eg. What are prominent features / landmarks of the area that could be used for background images?
- Sketch how current issues / events should be displayed on the website.
- What links should be available on the welcome page?
- How could social media feeds be viewed? Show on the welcome page then go into more detail on a separate page if required.
- Use the six to one design template (Buley, 2013) shown below : this encourages participants to squeeze out more ideas than they think they're capable of. The group (can include the rest of the class for this if you prefer) then decides which out of the 6 is the best one.

Figure 1.6 Six to One Design Template (Buley, 2013) and printed tablet template

At the end of the process (about 30-40 minutes) each group's ideas will be presented by a spokesperson from the group to the rest of the class. The group should decide together on which ideas are the best (from the six sketched).

1.5.1.2 Design for a specific person, action storyboard

Time approx. 30-40 minutes

Groups assigned one of the Young People or Policy Maker Personas and asked to:

- Sketch a quick storyboard for how this person could use the platform using your ideas from Task 1.
- Suggest any extra features that this person would find appealing.

Can again using a pre-printed template for phone / tablet if they like, then linked together to make the story. At the end of the activity, step through the ideas for the rest of the group.

1.5.2 Co- Design Workshop Mollet (Young People)

The methodology described above in 1.5.1. (General Methodology) was followed for the 2 Hour session carried out on 09/02/16 at the Mollet High school premises with 12 students from the school who were studying English and aged between 16-18 years old.

At the end of the first activity there was approximately 10-15 minutes left until the end of the class, which was not sufficient time to fully carry out the planned second task. Instead, this time was spent getting each group to think about a different idea. One group thought about how Policy Makers could interact with them using the platform, the second group thought about the interactions of young people using the platform and the third group thought about ideas for 'badges' promoting engagement with the platform and progression through different 'levels'.

The students who took part in this session were very engaged and some managed to write down their ideas in English, some were less confident in English, but still managed to convey their ideas effectively with some support in translating.

1.5.3 Co-Design Workshops Valdemoro (Young People) Series of four workshops.

The methodology described above in section 1.5 (General Methodology) was followed for the four 2 Hour sessions (2 groups participating in 2 sessions each) carried out in May 2016 at the Valdemoro Valle Del Miro High school premises. Twenty five students participated, the first group comprised 14 students. 13 male and 1 female, with 3 under 18. (17 years. N.B. Gender not balanced due to the technical nature of the course and the fact that less females took this class). The second group comprised 11 students, 7 male and 4 female. All of them more than 18 years old.

Tuesday, May 10:11th May 2016. At Valle Del Miro High School in Valdemoro.

Workshop co-ordinator: Amparo Ortiz and Gonzalo Martin. (Valdemoro Municipality)

Presentation, guidelines : Paula Forbes. Abertay University. Via Skype.

Paula Forbes presented the project to the students via a remote Skype presentation.

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- Group 1 - 14 students. 13 male and 1 female. 3 under 18. (17 years) 2 teachers from Vallé del Miro School. There was an uneven mix of genders due to the nature of the subject being studied by this class (computing) which tends to attract more males than females.
- Group 2 - 11 students. 7 male and 4 female. All of them more than 18 years old.

Figure 2.2 Photo showing one of the Valdemoro Co-Design sessions with remote Skype from Abertay University

1.5.4 Prague

The methodology described above in 1.5.1 (General Methodology). was followed for the 2 Hour session carried out on at the *Fair Food Club (Faculty of Sciences, Charles University, Prague)* with 7 participants aged between 23-28 years old. Gender 3 females, 4 males. Participants worked as 2 groups.

1.5.5 Hatay

The methodology described above in 1.5.1 (General Methodology). was followed for the 2 Hour session carried out on at the with 21 participants in Hatay Metropolitan Municipality aged between 18-28 years old. Gender 9 females, 12 males. Participants worked as five groups.

1.6 Workshop on Issues of Trust - Crete

The issue of Trust was highlighted during the first research phase of the STEP project as being vital to effective e-Participation. Trust is important in that the platform should appear 'trustworthy' and should enable trust between policy makers and young people to develop.

A workshop to investigate what kind of features would promote trust was therefore carried out with a mix of young people, public officers and policy makers in the Chamber of Heraklion, Crete. The session was led by Paula Forbes of Abertay University, supported by Machi Simeonidou, Panagiota Syropoulou (both Draxis) & Eleni Hatziyanni (ROC) during the session. The workshop comprised 22 participants, 10 female and 12 males. Age range was between 18 to mid-sixties. The group was a mix of Policy Makers (mainly from Heraklion Municipality) and students (most studying environmental topics, including some ICT students).

1.6.1 Trusted Websites

Participants were asked to consider and list (one site per post-it note) the online sites that they had provided with their personal details in the last 6-12 months. They were then asked to rank these by how trustworthy they believed them to be. Prior to the session, participant information sheets and informed consent forms (including parental consent if required for under 18's) were given out and then signed forms collected back in for our records.

Methodology:

Participants worked in groups of 4-6 and were given a brief 5-10 minute overview of the STEP project via a Powerpoint presentation explaining the aims of the project. An explanation was then given of the methodology below. For this workshop instructions were translated from English to Greek for the benefit of those participants who were not confident in English.

1.6.1.1 Brainstorm Issues of Trust

Participants were asked to:

- Individually: list all the websites that they have allowed access to their personal details within the last year (Post-It notes)
- In groups: State what they look for when using a website or app to ensure it is trustworthy? (Post-it Notes)
- In groups: Arrange these websites / features into categories

1.6.1.2 Card Sort - Issues of Trust

- Using the printed cards the issues were arranged in order of their importance. 3 groups: Very Important, Quite Important, Not that Important; then ordered within the groups.
- Blank cards were available to add any extra issues not identified in the first exercise (printed cards)

1.7 Role Play Exercise & Interviews Petitions – Calabria / Locride

The region of Calabria was keen to explore the issue of Petitions for their contribution to the Co-Design Process. An awareness campaign was created in the municipalities to ensure that the right to launch a petition should become true right of all, and that young people were more informed on current environmental issues. A series of meetings with the municipalities, the local youth and the environmental organisations took place. A series of preliminary interviews were then held to

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investigate the creation and validation of the petition process, culminating in a role-playing exercise with young people. The role-playing exercise was made up of 15 (9F, 6M) people aged 20 to 35 years. They were informed and interviewed by Facebook and Whatsapp respectively.

Informed about the project	People that have answered the questions, and engaged with environmental issues (signed the petition)	Workers	Students	unemployed	Retirees	who have signed a petition	Administrators in the municipality
445 people by social network	245	38%	31%	16%	15%	200 on 245 answers	10 interviewees

Table 1.2 Number of people involved in STEP activities in Calabria

1.8 Hot Chocolate Workshop (Young People with less opportunities_Dundee).

1.8.1 Methodology:

Workshop held on 14th December 2016 at one of the Youth Group's Open Sessions

Run by Paula Forbes & supported by Kirsty Evans (Abertay University volunteer student)

Open Sessions are informal drop-ins where young people come to build relationships, have a safe place to be, develop new skills and explore new ways of thinking. These happen on Tuesdays & Wednesdays 7-9pm and Saturdays 2-5pm. <http://www.hotchocolate.org.uk/>

Attendees: approx. 15-20 young people aged between 15-21 years old

The group works with young people ages 12-21 who hang out in the city centre (around 150 different young people over the course of a fortnight). They don't 'put stuff on' for the young people, instead they support them to develop their own opportunities – that way more skills and confidence are developed. Their vision is to see young people on their journey...

- choosing engagement, future, potential
- developing resilience, confidence, self-knowledge, purpose, broad worldview
- becoming positive change-makers, community builders, mature citizens

'Hot Chocolate is open to all young people without prejudice or distinction of religion, race, culture, health, disability, gender, sexuality or politics. The only restrictions are of age: secondary school age up to 21 years old.' (Taken from the Hot Chocolate website).

This workshop had to be modified from the methodology used previously, ie the format of formal presentation to the group and then the whole group working together simultaneously, as the informal nature of the drop-in session was not compatible with this method. As this workshop also took place late in the process it was decided to concentrate on validating the existing functionality and design ideas already implemented and to try and gauge the likelihood that young people would be prepared to use the platform.

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The lead researcher arrived at the youth centre an hour ahead of the Open Session to meet with the team and youth volunteers who were able to inform her about the nature of the sessions and the young people who attend. A student volunteer arrived about 15 minutes before the session and then both were briefed on the format of the Open Session.

The centre was made up of several rooms, including a dedicated Art room, a Music room, a Sports room and a Chill Out room. The research team initially located themselves in the Chill Out room with some promotional STEP material and a laptop, phone and tablet device to showcase the STEP platform and to gather feedback. It was necessary to move around to visit the other rooms however as the young people tended to stay in a specific area and it was clear that we would need to move to where the young people were to engage with them, they weren't going to come to us.

Initially the young people were quite hesitant to engage with the research team but with the help of a plentiful supply of Chocolate and some gentle introductory conversation, engagement was achieved and some were willing to listen to us explaining the aims of the project and to have a look at the platform. It was necessary to work in very small groups (2-3 people) and it was quite a challenge to stay on topic as the young people were very exuberant and keen to continue their conversations and socialise with the other young people.

The people engaging with us were aged between 16 and 21, and were an even mix of genders. The group has a high percentage of LGBT young people who enjoy attending as they feel much more accepted than they are in the wider community. Once the young people began to speak with us they were very open and shared some of their experiences in a humorous way. One of the young males (age about 20) was very interested in the interface design and gave us some excellent feedback.

This workshop generated less material overall than the others, but the feedback received was valuable and helped to validate some previous findings.

1.9 Policy Maker Workshop Valdemoro

1.9.1 Mapping the User Journey

1.9.1.1 Methodology:

- The activity was introduced and a brief overview of the STEP platform given to the participants.
- Participants were divided into teams to discuss personas, motivations fears and goals.
- The persona's goals, motivations & frustrations for achieving their key goals were discussed in the group (For this activity we focussed on the Wind farm Scenario).
- Start and end points for the user journey were defined. Each group mapped out the tasks, steps, phases, transitions and anything that described the user experience in achieving their goal.
- The journeys were then shared with the larger group, highlighting where they think STEP could effect real change or add value and also raising any issues which required clarification (eg. need to know: whether the users can be anonymous or not, how the platform will be linked with any existing websites of the authorities, etc.).
- Design Challenges / Clarification Points were highlighted and mapped onto the user journey. Cards added above the grouped post-it notes to identify key functionalities and/or uncertainties

2 Results of the Co-Creation Workshops

The total number of young people and policy makers involved in the Co-Creation process was 162, consisting of 99 males and 63 females (see table 1.1 for a more detailed breakdown). Here the results of the individual workshops will be presented and general conclusions discussed later in the Deliverable.

2.1 Workshop on Youth Engagement Dundee

The first workshop focussed on ensuring that the platform would be as engaging as possible for young people. This session, which was undertaken with first year game design students, generated a huge amount of material. The group were very engaged and as the students were embarking on a creative course (Computer Game Design) they were very creative and skilled in conveying their ideas.

2.1.1 Appealing Design Ideas / Mini games

For the first activity participants were asked to come up with some appealing design ideas or mini games with an environmental theme.

Some Comments on Using the Platform:

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- Getting started should be easy! First let the user design their post, then you ask them to register with their email – that’s it.
- Platform should have the ability to upload your own posts with images of issues or of you and your friends making a difference. Link Posts to existing Social Media.
- Ability to upload your own posts with images of issues or of you and your friends making a difference. Link posts to Social Media.
- People should have the ability to start polls (petitions) and have their say in local events.
- Should be two categories: ‘Local’ and ‘Global’.
- Collage interface in the line of Tumblr and Pinterest.
- Connect people around the world, for support, advice and general encouragement.
- Provide contact info for environmental organisations and allow them to advertise for help / support.
- Give people the option to participate in charity events / fundraisers for environmental organisations.
- User Accessibility: Colour scheme should be suitable for colour blind & visually impaired. Sections should be clearly segregated and described (compatible with screen readers).

2.1.1.1 Best Idea List – Engagement Features

Group 1: Eco-City

Sim City Type game, need to balance the population with the energy demand. If emission levels get too high you lose points, can balance production with solar panels & other renewable energy sources. City progresses on its own over time, but requires regular interaction.

Group 2: Growing Tree Game

A tree stump that has mini games growing from the stump, as you unlock the games the tree grows unlocking more games etc.

Group 3: Social ‘Pinterest’ Board

Read about local events, posts about fly tipping etc. Links to petition sites – easy to post to Facebook.

Group 4: Recycling App.

App showing how much stuff has been recycled. Collective action with a reward once you get to a certain level – eg a 3d printed action figure (made from recycled plastic). Tracked by photos?

Group 5: Cookie Clicker Game (could be recycling theme)

There could be an international leaderboard showing which countries are recycling the most. Could also provide information on what the different types of plastic can be recycled into. Could link real action into the game, tracking progress towards goals.

Group 6: An interactive, animated site.

Click on objects to get information and links to mini games. Game set world, user finds the games as they explore the site.

Group 7: Drawing competition – aimed at younger demographic.

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It could showcase drawings, they could be done on digital packages or by traditional methods & then scanned in. The drawings would be educational and the site would provide more information on the issues in the pictures – eg animal conservation, endangered species, climate change etc.

Group 8: An interactive site with a very clean interface. Some video links and some games, but it should be easy to find information. The site should be clean, but colourful and as simple as possible. Had looked at some environmental sites and the general opinion was they were quite old fashioned and cluttered. STEP site should be different and more attractive.

Group 9: Conservation Challenge

A site with cartoon mascots (eg of endangered animals, Panda, Tiger etc.). When user clicks on the mascot they get information about the species and also a link to mini-games. Eg Bamboo Challenge game. Panda wanders about collecting bamboo, but it gets sparser and sparser, at the end of the game you get information and a video on what is happening to protect pandas.

Other Interesting Ideas Generated:

Fishing Challenge: Fisherman trying to catch fish – endangered sea creatures keep getting attached to the hook. Divert the endangered species by clicking on them.

Tree Protesters: Protesters are trying to keep the forest from being cut down, try to keep the protestors from leaving by bringing them food and water. Enthusiasm level bar shown next to each one.

Recycling Bin Challenge: Get the rubbish in the correct bin as it drops down the screen.

Growing Challenge: Provide light, correct temperature, CO2 levels and nutrients to plants (suggested trees but could also be crops that people harvest). As the game progresses levels may become more unfavourable (eg increasing temperature, decreasing nutrients) making the game harder.

Game similar to Breathingearth.net: Shows people how much they are wasting. Current population levels etc.

Game similar to Freerice.com: Games that actively affect positive change. Click on the right answer: If you get it right, you get a harder question. If you get it wrong, you get an easier question. For each answer you get right, we donate 10 grains of rice to the United Nations World Food Program.

Safari Game: Player walks around trying to find animals in their natural environment. When you find an animal you unlock new information about the animal. You can find endangered animals (rarer and harder to find); when you find them you find out about what you can do to help.

Collage Interface (similar to Tumblr & Pinterest): Ability to upload your posts with images of you and your friends making a difference – links to social media. Two categories: Local & Global. Easy to use & register. Provide contact info for environmental organisations. Organisations are able to advertise for help. Options for getting involved in local events etc.

These ideas are clearly not associated with any of the Pilot areas, but are more general ideas for how the site could possibly be made more engaging to young people.

Game similar to Dumb Ways to Die: This was an Australian public service announcement campaign by Metro Trains in Melbourne, Victoria, Australia, to promote rail safety. The campaign video went viral through sharing and social media starting in November 2012. “The aim of the campaign was to engage an audience that really didn't want to hear any kind of safety message, within two weeks, it

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had generated at least \$50 million worth of global media value in addition to more than 700 media stories, for "a fraction of the cost of one TV ad".

<https://itunes.apple.com/gb/app/dumb-ways-to-die/id639930688?mt=8>

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Dumb_Ways_to_Die

A Twitter Mobile Styled News App.

- Newsfeed appears and user able to navigate to areas of interest via tabs at bottom of screen.
- When first starting the app you create an account, you are asked about what areas of information you are interested in. Tailored info then provided. Location is also set and you can find info about local issues/events.
- Social Media integration for sharing stories etc.
- Heatmaps to show what environmental issues are currently popular topics. EG UK red for 'climate change' Italy blue 'animal rights issues'.
- Able to set up summary options so that top stories whilst you have been away appear at the top of the newsfeed.
- Can also get the top stories emailed/texted to you to read.

2.1.2 Designing for Young People using Personas

2.1.2.1 Design for Sophia Papadakis

For Sophia the design ideas were to present the latest **news** about global science and environmental developments. A **calendar** highlighting relevant events where you can **search for local or global events** and volunteering activities. The ability to **start petitions** and to send to the relevant authority once enough signatures are reached, allowing users to express their voice. Areas of the site are **Region Specific**, should include reports on what has been done via **local initiatives** and projects (eg. How much money spent on recycling in the local area or what green energy plans do they have here).

A **language translation feature** to encourage international communication between users.

In addition to the above features the group suggested linking to recycling / second hand sites (eg. Freecycle) and **encouraging sustainable transport** by linking to carpooling applications.

Blogging type facility – giving her a platform to communicate her ideas to a wider audience. It should be easy to create and share tips for saving the environment. Site should have a Social Media Presence and use **Hashtags** that relate to environmental concerns/issues. It would be nice to link to the user's Instagram account.

Somewhere similar to ETSY for selling local homemade crafts. Opportunities for better Education, eg. Scholarships, different courses (related to the environment) in different countries. Links to environmental jobs and Eco-volunteering programmes.

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Figure 2.1 Idea Generation for Specific Personas – Sofia Papadakis.

2.1.2.2 Design for Michael Cordona

- A Twitter Mobile Style news app where your newsfeed appears in the middle of the screen and you can navigate to find areas of interest via an interest tab or search located at the bottom of the screen. Clicking the headline gives you the story and the link to the original source.
 - On starting using the app you can create an account, you are asked about what types of information you are interested in to enable the newsfeed to be tailored to the user, eg. Michael isn't that interested in the political side of things.
 - Ability to set location, to allow information about local events and issues. This can be a separate tab. You can also see what is going on in other countries.
 - Social Media integration – so that you can easily share/retweet specific stories / causes that you are interested in.
 - Heatmaps to show what environmental issues are currently popular around the world. Eg. UK may be 'red' for Climate Change' whilst another country may be Blue for 'Animal Rights' issues.
- Ability to set up summary options to allow the top stories to appear at the top of the newsfeed while you have been away. Option to get top stories sent via e-mail/text alerts.

2.1.2.3 Design for Daniel Weber

- Prioritise the **Debating** Features of the App.
- Allows the user to set their **profile**, including name / username, age and the area they live.
- GPS oriented (can choose a radius to allow responses from specific regions)
- Pose new Questions:
 - Time Limit
 - Based on location
- Ability to join an ongoing debate in the area
- Questionnaires via the site
 - Multiple choice answers
 - Set priorities for future debates etc.
- Feedback
 - Comments
 - Voting
 - Share results via other Social Media (Twitter etc).

Infographics:

- Keep things clear
- Catch Readers eye
- Make it fun

Interface:

- Clean / Simple
- Easy to use
- Pictures / Images
- Use of colour (pastel colours)

Demographic:

- 16-29
- Educational / Fun

Social:

- Images of who is posting and what is happening
- People sharing their stories of environmental experiences to encourage other young people to 'do their bit'.

2.1.2.4 Design for Jan Cerny

Figure 2.2. Sketches & notes made in Designing for Jan Cerny

Other features to include for Jan Cerny would be:

- Ability to **create a group** via the site to allow reaching out to youth for arranging activities etc. (outside social media). A forum / **chat** site to start dialogue with new and different people.
- Option of small subscription to site with the money going to environmental causes. The site could possibly help to **raise money** for environmental activities and trips. Aim to get people to think more long-term about the environment.

2.1.3 Policy Maker Design Ideas:

2.1.3.1 Design for Maria McKay

For Maria the website needs to be **Easy to Use** and should feature **Video Tutorials** to learn about the features of the platform and how to use them. Platform should be ‘foolproof’ and easy to navigate. Platform / App should be linked to Social Media. Features for supporting Real World Events such as volunteering. Information on waste provided to young people should be **relevant to their lives**, eg. How much metal /plastic not able to be recycled for old phones, hair straighteners etc. Gamification features such as: Country leaderboards for recycling / CO2 emissions.

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Figure 2.3 Notes made designing STEP platform features for Maria McKay

Features of the Platform should include:

- Comments / Search Features
- Map and Contacts section
- Forum / Chat for people to talk about organising group events etc. (volunteering)
- Group days to reach people in need (eg. Elderly, people needing help with recycling etc.)
- Reporting section for the local area (could alert local authority about areas in need)
- 'Hard to Reach' groups could request help via the site
- Feedback section

2.1.3.2 Design for Albert Sayago

An ideal platform for Albert would include:

Information on **Smart Cities** (could highlight a 3D model of an ideal smart city), highlighting the different features, explain how it improves transport, energy saving etc. Good to raise awareness.

City Profiles – allow people to see which cities are smart and what they are doing well, also what they need to improve. This could help to raise awareness of novel energy efficient transport systems (eg the Vac Train <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Vactrain>).

Could be an interactive feature to increase engagement eg. Build your own Smart City. Could be shared via the platform and this could encourage interaction with other citizens. Helps to highlight the issues they think are important.

Could also link to an energy tracker app – citizens could share to the platform or social media when they improve their energy efficiency – good for engaging friends.

Politician Profiles: This could link to existing Facebook profiles (or the profile set via the STEP platform), you could allow people to tweet or **send questions** to policy makers via the platform. The site could provide tips on 'How to engage with Politicians / Policy Makers).

Site should allow polls (and petitions) to see what issues citizens find important.

2.2 Personalisation Pilot Partners / General Co-Design Platform

2.2.1 Mollet del Vallès

Figure 2.4 Example of Co-created Landing Page for Mollet del Vallès

The Young People from Mollet del Vallès High School were very enthusiastic about the platform and generated very colourful and imaginative landing pages demonstrating the features that they would like to see on the platform. Some very detailed sketches were drawn, features included:

- Leaderboard (points based on activity & likes / comments)
- Projects / Events area
- News Feed
- Number of users
- Links for sharing via Social Media
- User Activity History – shows when items have been shared via social media
- Local Weather
- Tabs: Notices/Images/Services Activities/Games/Causes
- Information on Gallecs*
- Links to other countries' sites
- Inclusion of local symbols
 - Windmill
 - Fish

*Gallecs is a rural area between the towns of Mollet del Vallès and Parets del Vallès that includes a natural area of 755 hectares. <https://ca.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gallecs>

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Fig 2.5 Some example drawings of the Mollet Del Vallès landing Page highlighting features

Fig 2.6 Some photographs of the Mollet del Vallès workshop.

The group who looked at how Policy Makers could interact with the platform suggested the following:

“If I were a politician I would set up a challenge via the STEP platform (with a tag similar to the Hashtag in Twitter) then you could for example, take a selfie planting a tree. I would also be interested in the latest events and projects and the latest news. I would create an Event or Project and talk with the people who have the best ideas to see how we can make them come to life. I would share these articles via the City Hall website too.”

2.2.2 Results - Valdemoro Young People Co-Design Session

2.2.2.1 Brainstorming Post - its.

- A place for giving our opinion about the platform.
- A good menu where each item is indicated clearly.
- Thumbnails adapted to each theme, to attract people.
- Attractive design and colours. (Repeated three times)
- A dedicated server platform.
- A chat feature to talk with other users, also in other countries. (Repeated three times)
- Language translator. (Repeated four times)
- Upload photos and videos. (Repeated twice)
- A forum so they can leave opinions. (Repeated twice)
- Good connectivity and social networks used (Twitter, Instagram or Facebook). (Repeated twice)
- Have initiative and freedom to interact with the government.
- Some Games, Indie games. (Repeated twice)
- No advertising or publicity. (Repeated three times)
- A clean, minimalist, simple and youthful interface (Material Design). (Repeated twice)
- The design is inspired by social network sites.
- Rewards, Prizes, discounts in activities for the best users who care for the environment. (Repeated twice)
- World News.
- Not looking for raising money, but ability to receive donations.
- A space for exposing opinions, giving ideas or asking and answer questions that may improve environmental conditions of the municipalities.
- A space where you can learn techniques to improve or optimize work in favour of the environment.

Conclusions - The most popular comments were:

- An attractive design, but at the same time, it was a simple interface aimed at young people.
- No advertising and with its own server.
- Chat to interact with other young people, especially young people from other countries therefore stress the importance of a language translator.
- Differentiate the chat forum. From the forum dedicated to requests or suggestions to policy makers. More institutional.
- Games and mini-games. Related with STEP issues. Catchy games and games to encourage return visits. For example, keep a plant, clean up garbage, etc.

Other Interesting Comments:

- Space for giving an opinion / feedback about the management of the platform.
- Space where you can find recommendations for improving the environment.
- Crowdfunding or some kind of donations or awards that are given to the platform.

Figure 2.7 Valdemoro Workshop in progress

Fig 2.8 Post-It Note Brainstorming at Valdemoro

2.2.2.2 Valdemoro Group Activity.

GROUP 1

- Chose bright colours - related with nature - green, orange and pink.
- Other colours apart from blue - which is the most popular in social networks nowadays.
- Note interesting publications or things trending or are popular now.

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- Simple interface.
- Popular publications.
- Best publications (photos, videos, etc.)
- Citizen's news.
- Forum and chat.

GROUP 2

- Few colours and little images. The images are provided for young people with their publications and videos they upload or share.
- Being able to manage the profile and to suit according their tastes.
- Highlight the opinions of young people and sharing ideas.
- Games that can be used directly on the platform or every time you go to recycle, you can download a code to get a game.
- Social networking, recommendations and Chat.

GROUP 3

- Giving importance to image project, logo, etc.
- A cloud icon linking the most important aspects of the platform:
- 'About Us' section - to discuss the project.
- News and publications.
- Chat
- Image gallery
- Contact.
- Highlight the importance of a space in which to view other petitions and meet other young people from other municipalities and other countries.
- Section for configuring language, notifications, project, etc. (Preferences).
- User tutorial to learn how the platform is used.
- Feedback- Receive answers from the policy makers according to requests.

GROUP 4

- The user, registration, settings and a menu where you can quickly go to the timelines of each of the options. (News, recent photos, videos, etc.)
- Items where the images are important.
- 4 basic colours with a bar that highlights the search.
- 'Close to you' feature: for upcoming news. Browse by location.
- More popular: Select for different content.
- Recent. The latest information is uploaded.
- Discover. Find other proposals or petitions.
- Upload photos to the platform with 2 or more filters that are related to environmental content.
- Find friends who are in STEP or invite them to join the platform
- Events where you can participate for improving the environment.
- Camera integrated to make photos and upload them.
- A map to search news, places, friends, etc.

2.2.2.3 Conclusions

Even though the young people said the design should have simple colours - once we gave them markers, they used very strong colours. We talked about it and reaffirmed that they can't use strong colours when it comes to design social networking or platform.

Most of the comments highlight the priority that is given to the images and videos.

Some designs highlight the interaction between young people and policy makers. They **prefer chat for other young people** and **a forum for policy makers**. They think that is quite important to have **contact with other countries** through search tools, maps, etc.

Many comments suggested the importance of environment-related games as an attractive activity for youth engagement.

2.2.2.4 Valdemoro Follow-up Workshop

Worked on Local Environmental Issues and Concerns and the Participation of Young People in Valdemoro. Participants were divided into small groups (3 to 4 people). Post-it's were provided and they were asked to highlight environmental issues that concern them. Afterwards the groups were sub-divided into 2 for a role playing exercise. One half represented the policy makers and the other half young people. The groups then debated on how to raise one of the environmental concerns highlighted earlier and the answers given by local politicians.

Requests or issues raised by the class:

- To promote activities for waste collection and awareness among young people of the damage of contamination.
- To create a new system of street cleaning.
- To put more fines or sanctions to people who do not respect the environment.
- To provide more outdoor spaces to play sports.
- Greener buses and encouraging the use of public transport.
- Recycling -containers provide rewards such as: discounts, movie tickets, etc.
- To involve young people to recycle waste generated after the holidays, concerts, etc.

Debate: Chose - the issue of waste collection at Social Events aimed at young people.

Young People Proposals. Making requests or petitions through STEP platform:

- To provide young people with bags so you can put bottles and glasses when the party ends.
- More recycling containers around the event taking place.
- They could get food or a prize for recycling.
- A group of young volunteers go the next day to pick up trash in exchange for some benefits, awards, etc. This option was not considered very viable, as it seemed a better choice to clean at that moment rather than later.

Policy Maker Proposals.

The Most interesting proposal here is to stop performing parties / events if young people do not collect waste.

2.2.1.5 General Conclusions:

Work with the groups was very positive and the young people were interested in the project and the activities they participated in. By creating a platform to encourage the participation of young people they really believe that with such a tool, it can be easier and more attractive to participate, not only in environmental issues.

In general, there is a lack of confidence in politicians and the belief that things will be resolved. They think that politicians are not interested in these issues and they do not care what young people think. Interestingly, when young people role-play a political role, they reacted with a very strong personality and gave sanctions instead of options.

2.2.3 Results Co-Design Workshop Prague

Workshop organised by Youth Environment Europe, took place at the Fair Food Club (Faculty of Sciences, Charles University) – 4th May 2016

The age range was 23-28, as following: 1 participant 23 years old, 2 - 24, 1- 25, 2 - 26, 1 – 28.

Gender: 3 females, 4 males.

Open discussion with the group after Task 1 (Design a Welcome Page for the platform):

Group 1 (3 people in the group) – discussed in the small group and came up with one idea.

- Large circle in the middle with smaller circles around; for each smaller circle: “general, more often found problems and inside you can go in more depth about how to tackle smaller problems correlated to the general idea”; everybody can click and check each topic

Question from other group: “how will it look on mobile?” – may be difficult to navigate

- On the background – map of the area/locality; mark different issues on the map in different colours; you can zoom out to the region/national level/European level and you can still see the issues in other parts
- “Local language mutation” – the page should be in the user’s language (this case, Czech) but also in English
- Search button
- News feeds to mobile (application)
- Registration to be on central level so that people can access more problems
- The platform should be attractive
- Maybe not managed by municipalities

Group 2 (4 people in the group) – at the beginning they each worked on their own idea, then they discussed each idea in the group and came up with conclusions using all 4 ideas.

- Design must be clean, in “**clean colours**”; **no green colour**
- Have **similar design for all municipalities** – [participants liked this idea]
- Have a main page where you can find your municipality and country
- No political parties involved; there could be a “third party” involved (e.g. related to an EU body) to monitor the platform/check that the platform is not misused by the municipality

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- Platform must have a lot of **concrete information** – e.g. **graphs, map, numbers** (“this year we lost 50% of the green area”); for this information should be in contact with academic institutions, environmental NGOs
- Section with “**what was done**” [in the municipality]/ “**what will be done**” next
- **Idea A:** Word cloud – to know what the **current issues** are; **news feeds**, updates from the community; **public budget should be available** (makes the citizens feel included in their community; if they can see the budget “they know what to ask for”, what could be a priority
 - What we target
 - problems and solutions
 - knowledge
 - local happenings

Question from participant with idea A: how should this platform be different than Facebook? What added value will it bring? “You can also start discussions, interact, make polls, spread petitions etc. on Facebook”; “uncomfortable to check the platform” when you could use Facebook directly

- **Idea B:** First page – find your municipality; you are redirected to a second page with several sections; you choose a section (e.g. ecological/local issues) and you can see several issues with discussions/articles etc. on each section; likes the idea from Group 1 with the circles (“similar to a molecule”)
- **Idea C:** a space to promote **what is happening in your community**; links to local producers
- **Idea D:** main page – have a slider feature with all **current issues** in the area; have a section where you can **find people across Europe** on similar issues than the ones in your area **and chat with these people through the platform**, create work groups

Figure 2.9 sketches from the Prague YEE workshop

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This design mentioned the language translation functionality.

The four boxes were to highlight the four most commonly encountered environmental problems of the area. Clicking these would give more in depth information about how to tackle smaller problems related to the general topic.

Contacts to others was mentioned on another sketch. Have a place where people can meet to discuss problems and suggest solutions.

Highlight: What has been done/ What needs to be done/How much green space has been lost.

Platform should be clearly different from Facebook.

Fig 2.10 Sketches from the YEE Workshop in Prague

2.2.3.1 Conclusions from the Prague YEE Session

There are a few significant conclusions we could gather from this session:

- Young people living in Prague would like to have a say on environmental issues not only at the local level, but **also wider (national, European level)**. They do not see it as mandatory that citizens can be registered only to the municipality level; they should have **access to issues and events happening across Europe** as well.
- The platform should **have similar design for all municipalities**; this will give users **the feeling that they are part of/contributing to a bigger, more unifying goal**.
- There is still some **distrust in the idea that municipalities will be managing** such a platform. As municipalities are usually run by representatives of political parties, young people living in Prague fear that the political parties will use such a platform only to their advantage and not necessarily for what is best for the people. One participant stated that he *“fear[s] that this project will get the same <diseases> as the municipalities”*.

2.2.4 Results Co-Design Workshop Hatay

The groups of young people participating in the Hatay workshop proposed some interesting sketches and ideas:

- They designed the background colour as turquoise blue and they said that we just imagine an energetic and enjoyable page.
- They put on the top of the Hatay Step welcome page a quotation from Atatürk that means; **“The rising new generation, the future is yours! We created the Turkish Republic, and you are the ones who will raise and sustain it!! ”** Mustafa Kemal Atatürk.
- On the top right corner, they put a **Hatay map** and Turkey general map.
- This group said that, we want to see the all the **news and announcements** about the STEP project in the welcome page with colourful signs.
- They would like a similar logo for the welcome page as the Hatay Municipality Logo; that is a **green leave of Daphne**. The numbers on the Daphne leaf represent the dialogs and comments of the STEP platform.

Fig 2.11 Sketch of Daphne leaf showing links to different sections of the STEP platform

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- Some young people wanted to put some social messages on the first page. For instance, for children there is an **animation video** about the important of environmental values.

Fig 2.12 Sketch showing the split tree to represent the old and new aspects of the city

- They also added this **tree logo**. One side of the tree **expresses the old** and full of environmental issues part of the city and the **other part of the tree means that the new and developing part** of the city day by day.
- On this sketch the young people used the traditional writing signs to write the city name. They focused on the fact that **Hatay is a multi-cultural society** and that they **have lived together for many years in Hatay in peace**. The young people of this society are **ready to support and provide a better environment to live in**.
- They included a slideshow on the left part that includes the Hatay environmental and cultural photos.
- The young people were keen to convey positive environmental images of the local area

Figure 2.13 Sketch from the Hatay Co-Design Workshop showing landing page

Feedback on the Step.green website after it was demonstrated

The main comments are:

- They got a little bit confused, it seems to them **a bit complicated**.
- They **like the design**.
- They **didn't like the color**; it should more colorful (dominant colours like red and blue).
- We couldn't demonstrate the social monitoring tool but we explain them how it's going to work, they liked the idea.
- About: Ideas, petitions, environment consultation- it was mostly positive.

Overall the platform was well received by the young people of Hatay, but they suggested tweaks in the design (mainly colour).

2.3 Issues of Trust Workshop - Crete:

2.3.1 Results:

It was noted by some participants that they trust sites that sell important services rather than goods and they also trust the sites that they use more often (suggesting trust is earned by past positive experiences). Websites providing information services are usually well trusted, however the least

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trusted site seemed to be the Greek Taxation website (Taxisnet), but it should be noted that tax websites are almost universally unpopular.

Figure 2.14. The Crete workshop on Issues of Trust

Highly Trusted:

The most trusted sites are those dealing with financial services, ie Banks, Paypal

Heraklion local government site was trusted (many participants work for this establishment though).

Cloud Services eg Dropbox

Skype / Viber / WhatsApp (VOIP sites)

Charitable sites eg WWF.com / University websites

Intermediate Trust level

Sites selling Services – eg Flights

Email services (quite a range of Trust levels form High to Low); most trusted amongst them was Gmail, less trusted was Hotmail, but the values were quite variable.

Sites offering services for co-working (eg. Asana), work oriented Social Networking sites such as LinkedIn are trusted more than Facebook and other SNS. YouTube had mid-range trust levels.

Low Trust:

Least trusted sites were social networking sites (listed were Facebook, Twitter, Foursquare, Pinterest, Instagram)

Sites selling goods, Ebay, Alibaba express etc. Exception to the commerce sites being Amazon which is quite Highly trusted, perhaps as this site has been around for such a long time and may have been people's first experience with online shopping.

Greek Ministry of Finance taxation site (Taxisnet) was not trusted, and was frequently at the bottom of participants' rankings.

2.3.2 Exercise 2: Card Sorting

The second exercise involved sorting a list of features by their importance. Blank cards were provided so that participants could add features they felt were important but not present in the pack of cards.

After arranging the cards by the order of priority by each group, the top 5 cards were taken and considered together to see if there was any consistency with the issues being chosen as most important; the next 5 most popular cards were then also considered ie (items listed 6-10).

From these organised groupings the ranks were noted for each of the 4 groups and points assigned accordingly to give a numeric value (Maximum points =25 for appearing at the top of the list).

Points were assigned to the cards in two ways to compare the results, the first analysis was done by giving a score of 25 to the top ranked issue, 24 to issue 2, 23 to issue 3 and so on. As a comparison the the process was repeated again, but this time giving more weighting to issues in the top 5, with those lower down the rankings receiving substantially less points (see table 3.1).

This meant that there are slightly different end results, for example the issue of 'not too frequent contact' scored more by the unweighted method as it appeared frequently but lower down the list.

The following list did not give extra points for being in the top 5, just a cumulative score. The top score for being placed at the top of the list was the same (25 points per group) but those lower down got would receive more points due to the lack of weighting.

Rank	Unweighted value	Weighted value
1	25	25
2	24	22
3	23	19
4	22	16
5	21	13
6	20	10
7	19	8
8	18	6
9	17	4
10	16	2

Table 2.1 Points assigned to issues in weighted and unweighted scorings.

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Unweighted Value Top Ten

1. Feedback Given
2. Appealing Design
3. Accurate information
4. Concrete Initiatives
5. Not too Frequent Contact
6. Enjoyable to use
7. Security Badges displayed
8. Frequently updated
9. Customisable information
10. Presence on Social Media

Weighted Value Top Ten

1. Appealing Design
2. Feedback given
3. Enjoyable to use
4. Security Badges Displayed
5. Accurate information
6. Customisable information
7. Frequently updated
8. Presence on Social Media
9. Contacts easily found
10. No broken links

Figure 2.15 Unweighted values for top ten issues of importance for trustworthy websites /platform

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Figure 2.16 Weighted Value Ranking of top ten issues of importance for trustworthy websites /platform

Fig 2.17 Unweighted Values for Moderately Important Issues

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- They were able to see the prototype STEP platform as a tool to express their ideas
- They have met many other young people and met new associations on the environment
- They were the mouthpiece for a form of eParticipation
- With the group activities they have improved their skills

Participants realized that it was really difficult to make a petition because sometimes the number of people who must sign for a petition is more than the number of people who normally go to vote. For example it is possible to present a petition of 500 people, but the voters to elect the mayor, this year were only 412, so it is almost impossible to reach the 500 required for the petition.

For the first activity a real problem, "the creation of a landfill," was discussed, also because many interviewees answered that they sign petitions only very close to their realities. So we talk about recycling and environmental protection. For the second phase of role-playing: this was dedicated to the realization of the meeting between the Policy Makers and citizens.

By controlling the statutes of the municipalities involved, they have become accounts that is needed to change most of the statutes and make more meetings with mayors and administrators to raise awareness of the petitions and the importance of this right for citizens. The policy side is not very favorable to empowering citizens, as reflected in the selection procedures in order to petition and the lack of clarity in the rules to follow.

Based on the work in the territory they realized that to win the petition must create a lot of publicity, to convince the unfavorable people but also to bring more people online. The group of citizens took part in a simulation of the petition on paper (printed) in a very small town. A deadline for the achievement of the signatures was set and during the week people continued to send messages to sign the petition. Many people commented that they were not very willing to give their personal details, for this reason they don't sign petitions.

During the evaluation we noticed that an awareness campaign is vital because many people, most of all over 50s, do not know the petition. The only sites that are known are change.org and firmiamo.it, secure.avaaz.org.

Thus an awareness campaign was created in the municipalities to ensure that the right to launch a petition should become true RIGHT of all, and that young people were more informed on current environmental issues. A series of meetings with the municipalities, with the local youth consult youth and the associations that deal with environment took place.

2.5 Hot Chocolate Workshop (Young People with less opportunities in Dundee)

As reported in the methods section the format of the workshop with disadvantaged young people had to be adapted in order to engage with them. The session was a series of informal chats with small groups of young people to show them the platform and get their opinion on the design and concept, and to ask if they thought they or their friends would use it.

Use of Platform

All of the young people we spoke to thought that the concept behind the platform was good and that they would be interested in using it. They said that they would not currently be likely to engage in any kind of political interaction with the local municipality (Dundee City Council), although the young

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people who were over 18 had already participated in voting (some when they were just 16 years old for the Scottish Independence Referendum in 2014).

They reported that there was no way that they would attend a meeting to discuss local issues at a Town Hall for example, and that they would not be very likely to visit the local municipality website.

The young people were asked if they would be put off using the platform knowing that it was managed by the local council. They disagreed and suggested that it would be better *“That’s exactly the people you would hope to be listening”* (Young male, 20). They enquired **if it would be possible to ask questions to the local municipality** via the platform and actually seemed very keen to be able to do this.

The young people were interested in how the platform would be advertised, comments received were that it would **need to be advertised through the channels young people already use** and not just the local council/municipality site. They also mentioned advertising via posters around places that young people hang out (Youth groups/ colleges etc.) saying that sometimes this physical advertising ‘catches their eye’ more than a social media post – perhaps because you keep seeing a physical poster everytime you walk past it, whereas the social media post is a bit more fleeting and ‘disappears’ again.

Design of the Platform

The young people were mostly positive about the design of the platform, they asked about the target demographic and agreed that the design was well targeted at this group – being **colourful and engaging** but **not too childish**. A comment from one young male was that the site was **very well laid out** and he liked the fact that not everything was presented at once which made it better and not too cluttered.

The design of the posts **was likened to posts on social media sites** such as Facebook and they said it was **quite ‘familiar’**. It was suggested that the platform **should be clearly ‘different’ from other social media sites** and not be too similar to Facebook. The posting functionality was liked – ‘it’s a bit like adding a post-it note’ one person said. Comments were made on the ability to share to and from other sites *“Posts should be very easy to share – it should be quick and easy, maybe a bit like Upworthy where it’s just one click”*.

Features

The young people liked the text to speech feature. They also really liked the language translation feature saying that they would be interested in reading posts from other countries.

Chat room: – this received a mixed reception, some young people said they would use it others said not but thought that others they knew may be more inclined to do so. They were interested in how the ‘matching’ worked and wanted to know if they could initiate their own ‘wee chatroom’ themselves and choose themselves who to include.

Social Media Mining Tool: This was very well received; they particularly liked the option to browse other people’s searches. *“This is good if you are not looking for something specific. And just want to get a feel for things”* (Young female, 19).

Leaderboard: The consensus was that the leaderboard was a positive aspect and that its use might compel people to use the platform more. *“I’d quite like to see my name on there (leaderboard) – I think it’d make me use it more”* (Young female, 17).

Negative Issues Reported

Wording of tabs for posting: The young people **didn't like the term 'Ideation'**; why not just use 'Idea' as it's easier to understand.

Colour of the Social Media Mining Tool (SMMT). Feed feels a bit distracting. This was referring to the blue background. The Social Media Feed from the Website I was using initially linked to an older version of the SMMT. They prefer to know quickly and easily exactly where the post had come from (ie Facebook, Twitter) whereas the Crowley Green reference made it difficult to decipher the origins of the post). They **didn't like or understand the 'Crowley Green' reference** in the SMMT.

2.6 Policy Maker / Public Officer Workshop Results

All the Policy Makers / Public officers worked in groups with fellow regional colleagues. Some language issues had been overcome by translation by more fluent team members, translating instructions from English to Spanish/Catalan where required.

2.6.1 Mollet del Vallès

Mollet Policy Makers / Public officers are currently very engaged in both citizen consultation processes and environmental issues. Mollet took the user journey mapping exercise more literally than most other regions producing very detailed steps. In general the same overall processes as in Valdemoro are used, but the municipality of Mollet del Vallès are much more familiar with the public engagement /consultation processes.

STEP Platform User Journey:

- 1st Provide project information.
- Then run stakeholder consultation.
- Taken from the stance that the municipality need to get the project approved.
- Share characteristics of the wind farm, get people involved in the design and characteristics of the wind farm.
- Wanted to publish to social networks via STEP to increase reach / engagement.
- Want to use short text description, images, links etc.
- Would like to have predominant opinions, more mainstream opinions viewable by others
- Stakeholder consultation, has a second level of collaborative evaluation.
 - Second step is to arrange round tables / events to elaborate along with experts and other stakeholders.

Technical requirements:

- Mandatory to connect to population census.
- Option for settings such as age filter.

- In Mollet there is an electronic office as well as ID cards for Catalonia citizens.
- Strongly believe in the need to have some information available for the challenges. Young people need this information.
- Mollet wants to use the STEP platform with secondary schools. They are keen to collaborate with them and get them to use it as a tool.

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- Local government and Young People two distinct groups. Cannot really expect them to just interact amongst themselves. Would like the platform to help them to do this too.

2.6.2 *Valdemoro*

- Petition must be done via an official document, filling in all required fields, would need a code for the petition.
- Document then goes to archive and the area of the appropriate department, eg. things to do with the environment go to environment department, then they decide if it can be solved. Need to give an answer to the petition.
- Process is person manned not electronic currently. There is an online channel and an online form that is then emailed. A person then has to read the email box before the document can be sent to the correct department.
- Petition can be on any subject.
- No way at present to verify email for people submitting online. Need some system to verify the email belongs to a real person and not a bot.
- These emails are not tracked or processed in a formal way, this is done by staff in the departments.
- Difficult to generate stats to know number of queries received etc from the current system.

Valdemoro reported that STEP should be very useful for gathering data. The platform will help to show where the needs are. For decision making, typically the process described doesn't lead to a decision, but aims to try and get a solution.

If a citizen currently would like to submit a proposal to a political party, there is no formal way to submit ideas. The citizen would need to go to each political party in turn to show the problem.

2.6.3 *Calabria*

For the Calabria Policy Makers / Public Officers, then the Locride area priority is: Young People from Locride then others in the region (approx 150,000 inhabitants). Civitassolis.org (a young people association) is currently a major collaborator with the region and they plan to use this existing channel to embed STEP to get greater reach.

- Currently 2 kinds of petitions exist;
 - those requiring a budget (Special),
 - those that don't (General).Time frame is 30 days for both.
- Asking something important to do with the budget (Special) needs at least a 1000 signatures. Formal process to submit to city council who is then obliged to respond and propose a meeting within a month.
- For General issues the gathering signatures/support section can be missed out and can be registered with the President of the Council / Municipality.
- Any paper petitions are archived.
- The petition is then registered with a unique number (Chronological order for these), & Published on the Public Council noticeboard. By law this has to be published.
- Petition - Submitted with signatures and time stamped. No online option at present.
- Municipalities/ local council then evaluate the petitions.
- Document then produced 'order of the day', these are then published online, via the order of the day. (Council Website)

Key Outcomes:

- Calabria would like to make petitions entirely online.
- Municipality could decide if this is possible.
- Need to amend legal framework. Need a unique number for the item under consideration (this is possible) and at least 1000 signatures in chronological order. Can replicate this digitally – this could be possible using ‘blockchain tags’.
- User identification: Need to check citizen is living in municipality, ask for name and address? Is there a way to check the people are real? ID number etc. Currently use Change.org in an informal procedure. Done by declaration. Would require a system to check ID card used as a unique identifier.

Identified Risks

- Very high youth unemployment rate in the region.
- Most young people who would be the ones to participate in STEP leave the area to study or find work.
- Should ensure that youth leaders are included in the process to try and increase participation rates which could be low.

2.6.4 Hatay

- The current Political situation means that there is no consultation process. Therefore, the Government in power has all the power. Pilot partner is keen to use STEP to leverage the power of the citizen voice.
- Issues are sensitive. Young people are mistrustful of authority. Would not want to enter citizen number for example for verification process.
- Would like to enable young people to voice opinion on issues wider than purely environmental.

3 Informing the Development of the Platform

The varied Co-Design activities undertaken with a large selection of end users (both Young European Citizens...YEC's and Public Officers / Policy Makers) has informed the design of the STEP platform on many levels. In some instances it has simply validated the initial design ideas, but often entirely new functionality has arisen from the process (for example, Chat features, matching people with others across Europe and the ability to discuss ideas together in a small group).

3.1. Requirements from the workshops:

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Policy Makers and Public Officers from all regions were keen on the idea of some kind of training, they were especially on a workshop on how to use the STEP platform. Video conference facilities for a tutorial /webinar on how to use the STEP features were also requested.

As a result, the following Webinars were conducted: 'Social Media Monitoring Webinar': 19/10/16 at 13.00 CET and 'STEP E-Participation Platform Webinar': 27/10/16, at 12.00 CET.

Ideally after attending the workshops, then each region should try and launch a 'dummy / test activity' as soon as the platform is ready to do this to ensure all staff can use it effectively and that there are no technical issues arising.

Software Features:

- Add gender and age data to the registration process -> make this optional to add on municipality level
- Add a unique stamp to all petitions and signatures -> use blockchain tags
- Option to send popular petitions to the right department for review / handling... or raise and run consultation with department members online (round table) -> more advanced share feature
- Require citizen registrant number (Spain: DNI / NIE number) to verify user and allow posting of petition -> gather methods to gather and verify numbers per different nationality
- Archive posts/responses in a secure legal environment, option to add archive function and give option to export to local municipality server
- List/highlight petitions that have been selected in political decision, add a "Highlight this" option for presenting via a separate list
- Verification of mobile phone number + option to invite users via SMS -> add as feature
- Option for users under 18 with Parental consent -> add feature for this – connect to registrant number necessary
- Terms and conditions and Data Protection policy -> add feature for agreement templates for Municipality to select and adapt

The figures below show how the design ideas and user requirements from the various workshops fed into the Development process. Developers then created individual 'Issues' from the listed issues in the Report where appropriate.

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STEP Platform / SP-12

Pilot Personalisation Valdemoro

13 of 13 ▲ ▼

Edit Comment Assign To Do In Progress Done

Details

Type:	Story	Status:	DONE (View workflow)
Priority:	Medium	Resolution:	Done
Component/s:	e-Participation Component		
Labels:	None		

Description

Requirement Requests from Workshop held in Valdemoro in November 15 with Policy Makers.

Requests from Valdemoro Workshop:

- Add gender, age data to registration process -> make this optional to add on municipality level
- Archive in secure legal environment -> add archive function and give option to export to local municipality server?
MS Word Export
- Option for users under 18 with Parental consent -> add feature for this – connect to registrant number necessary?
Put age to the registration form
- Terms and conditions and Data Protection policy -> add feature for agreement templates for Municipality to select and adapt
Upload PDF with more specific terms and conditions.

People

Assignee: Trond Bugge
Assign to me

Reporter: Paula Forbes

Votes: 0

Watchers: Stop watching this issue

Dates

Due: 31/Mar/16
Created: 16/Feb/16 3:27 PM
Updated: 01/Jul/16 12:25 PM
Resolved: 07/Apr/16 12:35 PM

Agile

View on Board

Figure 3.1 Screen shot from Atlassian showing some Personalisation requirements for Valdemoro

STEP Platform / SP-13

Pilot Personalisation Mollet del Valles

Edit Comment Assign To Do In Progress Done

Details

Type:	Story	Status:	TO DO (View workflow)
Priority:	Low	Resolution:	Unresolved
Component/s:	e-Participation Component		
Labels:	None		

Description

Dear colleagues these are our personalisation requirements:

- 1- Display a "ranking of top users on the right side of Mollet page.
- 2- To share challenges on social media to promote interaction among users
- 3- Change the background image of Mollet page adding a weather forecast like the one's in Iphone. The idea is that the background will change during the day.

Figure 3.2 Screen shot from Atlassian showing some Personalisation requirements for Mollet

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The screenshot shows a JIRA issue page for the 'STEP Platform' project, issue ID 'SP-252'. The issue title is 'Feature to allow user to upload route maps via STRAVA /MapMyRide'. The issue is currently in the 'TO DO' status. The details section shows the following information:

- Type: Task
- Status: TO DO (View workflow)
- Priority: Medium
- Resolution: Unresolved
- Component/s: e-Participation Component
- Labels: API, compatibility

The description of the issue reads: 'It would be a nice feature if users could upload their existing route maps from cycling apps they may already be using. Useful for any municipality asking for new cycle routes / bike parking etc.'

The 'People' section shows the assignee as Caner Tosunoglu and the reporter as Paula Forbes. There is one watcher, Paula Forbes, who has chosen to stop watching this issue.

On the left side of the screenshot, a sidebar lists several other issues, including 'SP-253', 'SP-205', 'SP-206', 'SP-15', 'SP-18', 'SP-17', and 'SP-33', each with a brief description of the issue.

Fig 3.3 Screenshots showing how output from Co-Design workshops fed into the STEP Development Process in JIRA Atlassian.

3.1.1 Co-Design Features implemented in the STEP Platform

3.1.1.1 Young People Features Implemented:

- A Europe wide feature to allow Young People to see what those in different countries are saying/doing.
- Social Media sharing features (Twitter, Facebook, YouTube, Google Plus.)
- Option to view posts and browse the site without being logged in
- News Feed type functionality (covered by the Social Media Mining Tool- allows personalised feeds of Keywords of interest to the user)
- Like Button
- Comment
- Ordering of posts by Popularity / Recent / Nearby
- Display a "ranking of top users" (ie. Leaderboard)
- Ability to participate in Europe – wide STEP activities, not just local level – implemented the timeline activity to increase engagement.
- Chat / Matching up with other young people

3.1.1.2 In the Process of being Implemented

- User Tutorials / FAQ's

3.1.1.3 Young People Features that may be implemented at a later stage if money/time allows:

- Dynamic background image of Mollet page adding a weather forecast similar to the Apple iphone. The idea is that the background will change during the day.
- STEP SnapChat Filters
- Games – would need investment of time and money, but would increase engagement with the platform.
- Find a friend (find people you already know online to be able to contact them / invite them to join STEP)
- Upload existing route maps from cycling apps such as Strava that young people may already be using. Also useful for any municipality asking for new cycle routes / bike parking etc.

3.1.1.4 Policy Maker Features / requests Implemented:

- Physical Workshops to learn to use the platform
- Online tutorials/webinars to learn how to use the platform
- Addition of gender/ age/postcode area data to registration process -> optional to add on at the municipality level
- Verification of mobile phone number via SMS (needed for petitions)
- Option to invite users via SMS

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- Terms and conditions and Data Protection policy → feature for agreement templates for Municipality to select and adapt
- Informed Consent for young people taking part in the STEP research activities (links to Data Protection Policy).
- Export STEP posts to a Word Document (to comply with the legal requirements for saving the responses to any consultation).
- SMS verification of users (needed for petitions)

3.1.1.5 Policy Maker Features to be Implemented at a later stage:

- Require citizen registrant number (Spain: DNI / NIE number) to verify user and allow posting > optional feature.
- Option to send popular petitions to the right department for review / handling... or raise and run consultation with department members online (round table).
- Feature video explaining the STEP platform to be made and released prior to the Beta release of the platform.

3.1.2 Lessons Learned / Difficulties Encountered during Co-Design Activities

Reflections on the Difficulties in carrying out co-design with varied groups:

On reflection there were some practical difficulties encountered in working with a diverse range of participants in the co-creation activities.

- The level of English language capabilities was sometimes mixed, in some instances it had been assumed that English was understood to a greater level than was actually the case. This was overcome by having plenty of people available in the workshops who were able to translate, but it added to the time needed to run a session. Often time ran out for the final planned task in Workshops.
- The difficulty in quickly conveying what the platform would do before the STEP platform could be demonstrated. In some workshops we utilized the Scenarios and Personas developed for D2.2 to convey this message, but usually time only allowed for one or two of these to be read by the participants.
- Some participants were not used to working in groups, the majority of the co-design methods used a small group situation. This mostly worked well, but when people are unfamiliar with others in their group it can take a little while before they work well together.

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6 Appendix

6.1 Abertay Youth Engagement Workshop

Albert Sayago

Local events listings

Energy tracking App

- Share to social media when you are energy efficient to engage friends

Social Media

- Twitter - people can tweet him questions and see events and issues
- Post news articles to raise awareness

Smart City

- 3D Model of an ideal smart city
- Highlight certain features
 - ↳ explaining things about CO2 transport, street lights
- Raise awareness

Politicians

- P. Profiles

Facebook

- See profile
- Hold folks to see what citizens find important
- Post news articles to raise awareness
- Tips on how to engage with politicians

City Profiles

- See what cities are smart
 - ↳ What cities are doing well
 - ↳ What cities need to improve

Increasing awareness of novel energy efficient transport systems
ie- the Val train

Reddit

- Own subreddit
- AMA's

Game / Competition

- Build your own smart city
- Interaction with citizens
 - ↳ See what they find important

(Albert Sayago

Recently elected as a councillor and Politics, studied Computer E developer. Interested in how ne... improve the city. He is especially interested in Energy Monitoring.

Albert is the youngest councillor ever to be elected in the area and he is keen to breathe new life into local politics and to promote new ways of doing things. Given his background in technology he is ideally placed to be involved in promoting SMART cities and introducing schemes and projects to bring about positive change for local citizens.

Lives in: Valdemoro, Spain

Age: 29

Position: Councillor

Social Media:

Goals

- To centralise and make it easier for

Motivations

- Would like to involve citizens more in the projects

Frustrations

- There is still a wall between citizens and politicians. We

Phone
Layout

D2.2: User and Technical Requirements

(Michael Cardona)

Lives in: Mollet del Valles

Age: 23

Occupation: University Student Food Technology MSc in Barcelona, & also working as a waiter

Social Media:

Michael mainly uses the Internet via his smartphone, he regularly checks it throughout the day to keep up to date with what's going on - mainly on Twitter, the news App and checking Facebook updates. He uses time travelling from Mollet del Vallés to Barcelona checking out news and what friends are doing. Michael is not that interested in politics, but would like to help promote the local produce of his area.

Michael thinks that at a local level the environment is better now as we have been raising awareness and we are more conscious than we were 50 years ago. However, the threats to the environment are now greater and stronger than ever. Global warming is more of a threat and for example the increasing CO2 emissions of China.

Michael's main interest is in food sustainability, he is aware of soil contamination and the damaging effect of pesticides on the environment. He also believes in locally produced food which has a much lower carbon footprint. Michael is also concerned about the relationship between developed and underdeveloped countries and feels that we are just taking and not teaching what we should.

Michael would like the ability to be able to compare different countries to know how his locality is doing in comparison with other places & other countries. Food for example, could compare how our food production compares, we grow about 50% organic food here in M

Goals

- To encourage other

Motivations

- To promote the benefits

Frustrations

- Food Waste - when

- A Twitter Mobile styled ^{news} app where your newsfeed appears in the middle and you can navigate to find certain areas of interest via an interest tab or search tab located at the bottom of the screen. Clicking the headline gives you the story and link to the original source.
- When you first start the app you create an account, you are then asked about what types/areas of information you are interested in learning about so that your newsfeed is tailored to the user e.g. Michael isn't interested in the political side of things.
- You can set up your location if you want to so that you can also find out about local issues and events. This is in its own separate tab. You can also see what is going on in other countries.
- Social media integration so that you can share / retweet specific stories/causes you are interested in.
- Heatmaps to show what environmental issues are currently popular topics around the world e.g. UK may be currently be red for climate change whilst USA is currently blue for animal rights issues.
- Can set up a summary options so that the top stories whilst you have been away from the app appear at the top of the newsfeed. You can also get the top stories headlines emailed / texted to you to read.

JAN CERNY

Vote at end of Month
to see who gets
the money.

WHAT ENVIRONMENTAL
CAMPAIGNS/CHARITY
GETS CASH

o Something he can
post/contribute to
↳ a possibility to
create a group in the
website → allows long-
term reaching of youth
for activities and stuff
(out outside social media)
A monthly look
- Small subscription to
site. People's ~~to~~
~~to~~ money go to
donations.

CREATE

The website could help
merge fundraising for
fun trips and doing
activities to help
the environment
→ trick people to
commit more long-term

D2.2: User and Technical Requirements

(Jan Cerny)

Lives in: Prague
Age: 28
Occupation: : Works at a
local environmental NGO.

Social Media:

Jan works at a local environmental NGO. Graduated with a degree in Environmental Engineering from a University in Latvia. Also involved in a local Youth Organisation as a leader, he takes groups of young people to enjoy the outdoors and the local natural environment. He has recently moved to a flat with a roof garden is enjoying experimenting growing some vegetables & herbs organically. He doesn't buy a newspaper or own a tv but listens to music and the radio at home. He gets his news online and by following his interests on Twitter. Jan does use Facebook and Twitter, he accesses them from a computer, he also uses the internet quite a bit. He uses Facebook to stay in touch with friends but is not an avid user. Has to use it to inform the local youth group about upcoming activities. Jan was interested to see that local politicians seem to be using Twitter recently. Jan had previously used a Moodle (type of University Virtual Learning Environment) whilst he was studying to discuss environmental issues. The Moodle group was set up for the students but the discussion group was Public and you could discuss with other people from different countries. Discussions were mediated by a Webmaster who raised different issues. He enjoyed using the platform and would like to use the STEP platform to do this again. Jan recently got rid of his smartphone and bought an older type phone just to make calls he found the smartphone was too much of an intrusion and contributed to information overload. When he is outdoors he doesn't want to be online all the time.

Motivations

Frustrations

Difficulty in getting Young

Simple Website

o Forum - So he
can get into
dialogue with
new and different
people.

Jon Lemy

Infographics

- kinda fun ish
- keeps things clear
- immediately catches reader's eyes

Clean, simple interface

- Pictures
- heavy use of colours - ideally positive colours etc

Educational Computer game

Demographic - 16 to Late 20s

Educational, Clean, Block-colours, simple graphics - (Dumb-Ways to Die style)

Colourful FUN!
Easy user interface is important and pretty being on the site must be easy.

Cross off welcome screen and enter the site

Game on the screen as an extra to the user interface. Take keys and put them in the correct opening to find out if item is recyclable or not.

Summary of who and what is happening.
Transparent scroll button that only shows when cursor moves over it.

- Natural
- Herbs/Vegetables/Organics, growing
- Animals Land or Sea
- Activities for young people.

Social Media icons in rounded-blocks
Squares are not fun!

Lives in: Prague
Age: 28
Occupation: Works at a local environmental NGO.

Social Media:

Graduated with a degree in Environmental Engineering from a University in Latvia. Also involved in a local Youth Organisation as a leader, he takes groups of young people to enjoy the outdoors and the local natural environment. He has recently moved to a flat with a roof garden is enjoying experimenting growing some vegetables & herbs organically. He doesn't buy a newspaper or own a tv but listens to music and the radio at home. He gets his news online and by following his interests on Twitter.
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Motivations

Frustrations

Difficulty in getting Young

Forums on the site on different environmental topics, with which the different petitions regarding the issue can be started and signed.

Headlines on homepage to do with international environmental issues, which will cover the last month or so of news.

Option to post environment related photos on the site, which can then be linked to the user's Instagram.

Petitions on site can be sent to the relevant politician(s) once they reach enough signatures, thus allowing users to express their voice.

Language translating feature to help encourage international communication between users.

Area of the site are region specific. Gives reports on ~~what~~ how much money is spent on local initiatives and projects, e.g. how much money's put on recycling or what green energy plans do they have.

D2.2: User and Technical Requirements

(Sofia Pa

With the current financial crisis in Greece Sofia and her peers are very interested in policies which directly affect them and their families.

Sofia is still at school, currently taking exams, she hopes to become a teacher. She is applying for University but concerned about meeting the living costs while she is studying, she is considering moving abroad to study as she feels it may be easier to get part-time work to support herself during her time at University.

Sofia thinks that Crete is in need of recycling facilities and is aware that most of Europe already has segregated waste collection. She is keen to find out more information about how to set up such a scheme as her local area is very beautiful and attracts a lot of tourists in the Summer, the tourists however add a lot to the amount of waste produced.

She recently did an environmental project at school where there was an upcycling challenge. Sofia's group won the contest by making these planters / candle holders from old wine bottles. The restaurant where she works part-time now uses them. This gave Sofia a taste for making

Lives in: Heraklion, Crete
 Age: 18
 Occupation: School Student and part time waitress

Social Media:

Blogging mediums - giving her a platform to communicate her ideas to an audience

Easy to use website allowing people to create a share tips a tricks to save the environment

- Somewhere for her to sell some homemade crafts for a small income. ETSY
- Links to Job website in order to give her support during university.
- opportunities for better education e.g. scholar ships, different courses in different countries

eco-oriented volunteering programs

social media presence.
 Hashtags that relate to environmental concerns

D2.2: User and Technical Requirements

(Sofia Papadakis)

With the current financial crisis in Greece Sofia and her peers are very interested in policies which directly affect them and their families.

Sofia is still at school, currently taking exams, she hopes to become a teacher. She is applying for University but concerned about meeting the living costs while she is studying, she is considering moving abroad to study as she feels it may be easier to get part-time work to support herself during her time at University.

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Lives in: Heraklion, Crete
 Age: 18
 Occupation: School Student and part time waitress

what folks to see
important
most news articles
raise awareness
on how

News about the world and environment. Science and development in different areas that's ~~well~~ ~~connected~~ connected to nature and the world around us.

Calendar with events. You can search for local or global. Volunteering

The five latest events

~~The five~~ latest adds on second hand

Going somewhere? Carpool

short guide

15:00
13:00
15:00

Dioc

Identifying the issues
Examining the overall project planning and implementation
Representing the entire Commission towards the Commission and the public
Organising project meetings as a distribution of all reports
Coordinating the preparation and submission of the Commission reporting and evaluation

D2.2: User and Technical Req

(Sofia Papac

With the current financial crisis, she is interested in policies which d

Sofia is still at school, current teacher. She is applying for University while she is studying living costs while she is studying as she feels it may be easier for herself during her time at University.

Sofia thinks that Crete is in need of more information about the local area is very beautiful and the tourist however add a lot

Lives in: Heraklion, Crete
Age: 18
Occupation: School Student and part time waitress

Social Media:

She recently did an environmental upcycling challenge. Sofia's goal was to create planters / candle holders from things she works part-time now use better use the things being thrown away and share upcycling ideas with others.

(MARIA MCKAY)

- WEBSITE EASY TO USE - VIDEO TUTORIALS
- COMMENTS / SEARCH FEATURES
- MAP AND CONTACTS SECTIONS
- FORUM FOR PEOPLE TO TALK ABOUT ORGANISING GROUP DAYS ETC - volunteering
- GROUP DAYS TO REACH PEOPLE IN NEED - (elderly people needing help with recycling)
- REPORTING SECTION FOR YOUR AREA
- FEEDBACK SECTION

D2.2: User and Technical Requirements

(Maria McKay)

Maria is not really a big user of social media herself but the local Health Authority (NHS Tayside) does have a Facebook & Twitter account and aims to engage young people via Social Media

Maria has worked in her role for about 15 years, previously working in the NHS. She is involved with the city council as a Strategy & Performance Manager trying to reduce health inequality in the city. Maria would love to improve the local environment for the citizens of her city, to improve their overall health & wellbeing. She believes that access to open space and contact with the natural environment and being active is very beneficial. Trying to eradicate fuel poverty

The city council has a long history of community engagement, but with new strategies for empowerment we should expect to see a range of benefits: local democratic participation boosted; increased confidence and skills among local people; higher numbers of people volunteering in their communities; and more satisfaction with quality of life in local neighbourhoods. Better community engagement and participation leads to the delivery of better, more responsive services and better outcomes for communities. A recent example of the use of IT to increase engagement was wedundee.com a site set up to support the city of culture bid in 2013.

Lives in: Dundee	Motivations	Frustrations
Age: 48	• Constantly try and devise new ways to tackle very	• Reaching the hard to reach - those people excluded
Position: City Council - Strategy & Performance Manager		
Social Media: No use		
Goals		
• Improve young people's health and		

COOKIE CLICKER

Building Recycling Centre by awarding more points
Voucher incentives recycle X amount for water towards stores.
make recycling relevant to charity, i.e
< amount of PLASTIC/METAL goes towards
new phones / smartphones etc
APP

• HARD TO REACH CAN USE HELP FEATURES ON WEBSITE TO RECEIVE HELP

• VIDEO TUTORIALS / WRITING THE BLOG SITE

• REPORTING SECTION TO AID COUNCILS ETC TO AREAS IN NEED

App - similar to "Dumb ways to die"

MASCOT - Recycling bin

App - keeps user up-to-date with environmental references with statistics and facts.

Snapchat Geofilter bin you unlock everywhere you're at a Recycling Centre.

Environment friendly lessons for younger children
Bright posters/characters to engage younger audiences

Route-in-check environment-oriented games e.g. Shooting paper blower hoop into recycling bin

Social Media Tags #
Twitter #~~recycle~~
Snapchat giveaways

Prizes for donation / customer loyalty
e.g. stuffed animal, key chains etc for those taking part

Mini-lectures on how to be environmentally friendly for those who don't know - funniest through the basis w/ website links

Kids drawing Competition
- Get their drawings turned into posters
- win free merchandise

Amongst Catchy 90's kids rap (about environmental awareness)

People can start polls
and have their say
in local events.

Give people the option
to participate in
charity events and
fundraisers for
environmental organisations

Getting started should
be easy!
First you let the user design
their post, then you ask them
to register with their e-mail, that's it!

Two categories:
"Local" and
"Global"

Ability to upload your own
posts with images of issues
or of you and your friends
making a difference.
Link posts to social media!

Connect people (users)
world, for support, advice
and general encouragement!

Provide contact information
to organisations that
support clean environment
and similar events.

User accessibility
- colour scheme suitable for the
visually impaired
- the sections are clearly
separated and described

Bigger organisations
can go and advertise for
help they need. If it's for
emergencies or just something
they need.

A collage interface,
in the line of
Tumblr and Pinterest.

Video

Were Here

6.2 Pilot Personalisation Workshops

6.2.1 Mollet del Vallés

6.2.2 Valdemoro

Poca Publicidad

- Poder subir fotos
- Poder entablar conversación con gente de otros países.

- Poder subir videos y que comenten y den likes o dislike.
- Noticias del Mundo.
- Juegos Indie.
- Descuentos en actividades.

- Mejorar la interfaz (Mas sencilla y juvenil)
- Inspirarse en una red social
- Poder subir fotos.
- Recompensas, premios a los mejores usuarios que cuiden el medio ambiente

- Que no tenga publicidad
- Que tenga una interfaz limpia y minimalista (Material Design)

Un chat

Tiene que tener un foto.
Evitar anuncios.

Una bonita interfaz, que también busque la interacción entre los usuarios.
A nice interface, that looks for socialisation between the users of the app.

No tiene que buscar la recaudación de dinero, aunque sí aceptar donaciones.
I haven't be looking for money, but accept donations.

Christian Becerra

- Algunos minijuegos
- Tiene que llamar la atención a los jóvenes que tenga conectividad para que se comuniquen con Twitter, Instagram o Facebook.

Poner la página en más idiomas

- QUE LA PLATAFORMA ESTÉ DISPONIBLE EN VARIOS IDIOMAS PARA PODER LLEGAR A MÁS GENTE.

- UN APARTADO PARA PODER PREGUNTAR O

RESPONDER DUDAS SOBRE EL TEMA O RELACIONADO.

- UN APARTADO DONDE PUEDES EXPONER TU OPINIÓN O DAR IDEAS QUE PUEDAN MEJORAR LAS CONDICIONES MEDIOAMBIENTALES DE LOS MUNICIPIOS.

Daniel Flores.

Tener iniciativa y conexión con el gobierno para interactuar.

Daniel Flores

Expandirse por las redes sociales más usadas (Twitter, Instagram) y usar el español en sus videos de promoción en youtube.

Ciaj Centro de Información y Asesoramiento Juvenil
ciaj@ayto.valdemoro.org

- Hacer un diseño que sea llamativo, para atraer al público.
- Hacer un foro para que los usuarios dejen sus opiniones.

Ayuntamiento de Valdemoro
Concejalía de Juventud

Ciaj Centro de Información y Asesoramiento Juvenil
ciaj@ayto.valdemoro.org

Tiene que tener fotos y un chat para que la gente pueda compartir todo lo que quiera

Ayuntamiento de Valdemoro
Concejalía de Juventud

Ciaj Centro de Información y Asesoramiento Juvenil
ciaj@ayto.valdemoro.org

- Color que atraiga al usuario.
- Sonido dedicado
- Chat para comunicarte con otros usuarios.

~~la~~ idioma hablado para todo los países

Ayuntamiento de Valdemoro
Concejalía de Juventud

Ciaj Centro de Información y Asesoramiento Juvenil
ciaj@ayto.valdemoro.org

Miniaturas adaptadas a cada tema, para atraer a la gente.

Ayuntamiento de Valdemoro
Concejalía de Juventud

Ciaj Centro de Información y Asesoramiento Juvenil
ciaj@ayto.valdemoro.org

Un buen menú en el que indique bien cada tema

Ayuntamiento de Valdemoro
Concejalía de Juventud

Ciaj Centro de Información y Asesoramiento Juvenil
ciaj@ayto.valdemoro.org

Un apartado para que la gente opine. Sobre ella

Ayuntamiento de Valdemoro
Concejalía de Juventud

6.2.3 Prague YEE Workshop

lost 50% of the green area
ACADEMIC INSTITUTIONS

~~the~~ what was done
what needs to be done

places where ppl. can meet to discuss
search button

should be different from a fb page

Clean colors
 (NO GREEN)

NO POLITICAL PARTIES

GRAPHS, MAPS
 ex. this year we

6.2.4 Hatay Workshop.

Evren Gelecek
Gözetim

HATAY STEP GENÇLİK
MERKEZİ

L. Sayfa

Açın Gözetim

Bande Yarım!

KAMU SPOTU

Animasyon

Programın Amacı

Hatay için Önemi

Arka Plan Resimleri:

Dünya Beynî Dalı ve Hat Hilal Yürüteli
Pays Kalesi (Türkiye Kadını)
Hassa (İslamiyet Öncesi Çekirge yarımlı Mesafeler)
Eski Anı Olaya Sokakları

Kurtuluş Cad.
Cami kilise istan - Antakya

Hatay
görseli

Lü yükselen yeni nesil . geleceki sizindir. #
Cumhuriyet'i biz kurdük, Onu yükselteceki ve sürdüreceki
sizlersiniz

Hatay Haritası

Dil
=

Hatay'in Gevneligi , Hatay'in Gelecegi

STEP
HATAY

Yapilacak ~~Arayışlar~~

[]
[]
[]
[]

Giris

Posta =

Sifre =

Reytdaak isteminiiz

1

~~Dünya~~ ~~Arkeolojik~~
Yazitad ~~Arkeolojik~~
DeRen Sanindagi
(Arkeo plan parcali fotografi)

Hatay'in Gevneligi-gelecegi
video

Linkler

Hatay'in Gevneligi

Etik yapisi

www

6.3 Issues of Trust Workshop Crete –

Crete Issues of Trust Card Sorting Exercise

Important

Most Important

step Appealing Design
Website / App
B1

step Contact Details
Easily Found
B2

step Optimistic
Outlook
B3

step Trust Mechanism
in place eg. Trip
Advisor reviews
B4

step Feedback Given
(eg. email confirmation
account creation)
B5

step Profile of
Policy Makers
Available
B6

step Mobile code
verification
eg when you access
from remote computer
or not your usual
used location/device
B7

step Concrete
Initiatives for
Participation
B8

step Case Studies
Provided
B9

step ~~Too frequent~~
NOT
emails /
contact
B10

step Customisable
Information
(related to your
interests
B11

step NO
Broken Links
B12

step Partnerships
with Trusted
Organisations
B13

step Unbiased
Political Content
B14

step Clear Process
Actions
B15

step Inaccurate
Information
B16

step Security Badges
Credentials
Displayed
B17

step Enjoyable
to Use
B18

step Site Frequently
Updated
B19

Most Important

Most I

 Appealing Design
Website / App
A1

 Feedback Given
(eg. email
confirmation account
creation)
A6

 Appealing Design
Website / App
B1

 Presence on
Social Media
Media
A2

 ~~Unclear~~ Process
Actions
A9

 Contact Details
Easily Found
B2

 Site Frequently
Updated
A3

 Concrete
Initiatives for
Participation
A10

 Optimistic
Outlook
B3

 Website/ App
not too
Cluttered
A4

 Unbiased
Political Content
A11

 Trust Mechanism
in place eg. Trip
Advisor reviews
B4

 Enjoyable
to Use
A5

 ^{NOT}
Too frequent
emails /
contact
A12

 Feedback Given
(eg. email confirmation
account creation)
B5

 Accurate
Information
A6

 Profile of
Policy Makers
Available
B6

 INTERACTIVE
CONTENT
A7